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Where is the Exit?" An Exploratory Study on COVID-19 Exit Strategies in Italy From an Attributional Perspective

Maurizio NORCIA^{1*}, Elisa COLI²

¹MD, Institute of Cognitive Sciences and Technologies – Italian National Research Council (CNR), Roma, Italy. E-mail: maurizio.norcia@istc.cnr.it **ORCID:** 0000-0003-0128-1687

²MD, Institute of Cognitive Sciences and Technologies – Italian National Research Council (CNR), Roma, Italy. E-mail: elisa.coli@istc.cnr.it **ORCID:** 0000-0001-7055-2554

*Corresponding Author

Abstract

Introduction: This study investigates exit strategies from the COVID-19 emergency in Italy from an attributional perspective.

Methods: An analytical observational design was applied to a convenience sample of 648 Italian adults (68.9% women, Mean age = 34.9 years, SD = 12.8). Data were collected via a computer-assisted self-interview (CASI) and included attributional choices and semantic differential scales adapted from the Revised Causal Dimension Scale (CDS-II). Statistical analyses included descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and interrater agreement (Cohen's k) to assess consistency between theoretical and perceived causal dimensions.

Results: Three dominant strategies were identified: relying on expert advice (35.0%), adopting preventive behaviors (33.8%), and trusting vaccines (19.2%). These preferences highlight a strong motivation to act proactively, emphasizing direct reliance on experts while bypassing intermediaries, such as politicians. Causal attributions were analyzed using dimensions of locus, stability, and controllability, revealing that respondents predominantly viewed the chosen strategies as involving personal responsibility and controllable factors. Younger participants were more likely to describe attributions as permanent/stable, while older respondents emphasized temporary/variable attributions ($\chi^2 = 33.689$, $p = 0.006$). Differences were also observed in the controllability dimension, with extreme poles more frequently selected by younger (18–29 years) and older (60+ years) participants compared to middle-aged groups ($\chi^2 = 25.786$, $p = 0.057$).

Discussions and Conclusions: The findings suggest that high uncertainty, coupled with a serious health threat, has spurred individuals to actively seek information and engage in preventive actions. This behavior aligns with attributional theories, which connect causal attributions to emotional and behavioral outcomes. The study underlines the critical role of clear, accessible information in

managing public health crises. Recommendations include improving information quality, tailoring communication to diverse audiences, and leveraging dialogic communication strategies to reduce uncertainty. These insights may inform more effective policymaking and communication strategies to address future health emergencies.

Keywords: Causal Attributions; Causal Dimensions; COVID-19; Pandemic; Social Inference.

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INTRODUCTION

In March 2020, Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus, Director-General of the World Health Organization, declared that the disease caused by SARS-CoV-2 exhibited characteristics of a pandemic [1]. The containment measures adopted over the following two years significantly impacted individual and collective well-being on social, economic, and psychological levels. Beyond the immediate fear of infection, individuals faced the burdens of isolation, uncertainty, and the reconfiguration of personal and familial life projects [2-4].

Today, the situation has changed considerably. Improved testing methods (including at-home and salivary tests), promising therapeutic approaches, and the large-scale dissemination of vaccines—with over 13 billion doses administered globally—have reshaped the public health landscape [5]. Enhanced knowledge of viral transmission and risk factors has helped mitigate generalized anxiety and fear [6]. On the other hand, most of these solutions were (and still are, by their nature) a work in progress. The urgency of the pandemic necessitated accelerated development timelines, especially for vaccines. A prime example is Operation Warp Speed in the United States, which fast-tracked preclinical trials and manufacturing [7]. While the speed of vaccine development was essential, it also contributed to public concern, especially when compounded by inconsistent communication from institutions and anti-vaccination discourse [8,9]. In this context, newer concerns replaced earlier ones, maintaining a climate of apprehension.

The dynamics just described—namely, heightened uncertainty in the context of a serious and unexpected situation—together with the human aspiration to enhance one's understanding and exert control over one's environment, foster conditions ideal for cause-seeking behavior [10-12].

The current study aims to investigate this attributional activity in the context of the COVID-19 crisis, focusing on the explanations people offer for how the pandemic might come to an end. Understanding these explanatory frameworks is important not only from a theoretical perspective—illuminating the psychological processes underlying attribution—but also for practical purposes, such as informing public health messaging and policymaking [13,14].

Conceptual framework: Causal attributions and causal dimensions

Causal attributions are judgments people make regarding the causes of events or behaviors. These judgments play a central role in how individuals relate to the world around them. Often acting as 'naïve psychologists' [15], individuals are motivated by a deep need for understanding and control [16], engaging in cognitive efforts that resemble experimental reasoning [10]. Though this process is frequently influenced by cognitive biases, such as hedonic bias [17-19], it remains a powerful determinant of emotional and behavioral responses.

According to Weiner's framework [20,21], the key lies in the structure of the attribution, particularly along three dimensions, whose impact on an individual's emotions and behaviors is even greater than that of the attribution itself: locus (internal vs. external), stability (stable vs. unstable), and controllability (controllable vs. uncontrollable) [22]. These dimensions have been shown to shape not only how people interpret events but also how they feel and act in response [23].

Consider an illustrative example: a person is unexpectedly insulted. This surprising and unpleasant event is likely to trigger a cause-seeking process. One possible attribution might be that the insult was provoked by the individual's own prior behavior—an internal, unstable, and controllable cause. Alternatively, the person might infer that the offender suffers from a cognitive impairment—an external, stable, and uncontrollable cause. These differing interpretations lead to markedly different emotional and behavioral responses, such as guilt or empathy versus defensiveness or detachment.

The dimensions of attribution exert distinct influences. Locus affects self-esteem and emotions like pride or shame. Controllability is closely linked to the attribution of responsibility and plays a major role in interpersonal judgments. For instance, anger and avoidance are common responses when a harmful action is seen as intentional and controllable [24]. Stability, meanwhile, affects expectations about the future: stable causes lead to predictions of recurrence, which may engender either hope (in the case of positive outcomes) or helplessness (for negative ones) [25-27]. In practice, attributions often involve multiple dimensions simultaneously, leading to complex or even contradictory emotional outcomes. Weiner's attribution-responsibility-support model [28] highlights how these patterns influence interpersonal behavior: we are less inclined to help those we see as responsible for their misfortune, and more likely to offer support when causes are seen as uncontrollable or situational. This model applies to diverse domains, including attitudes toward poverty: believing that a poor person should not be held responsible for her condition but, say, attributing it instead to situational aspects, such as scarce employment opportunities, elicits a much stronger inclination to support that individual than if the individual in question is blamed for his condition [29,30].

At the intrapersonal level, internal and uncontrollable attributions for negative outcomes often generate feelings of shame and reduced self-efficacy, particularly when the cause is also perceived as stable ("What happened is my fault, and I cannot do anything to avoid it now or in the future.") [31,32]. In contrast, internal yet controllable attributions can foster motivation and proactive behavior [12,33].

Causal dimensions and health

Causal attributions have particularly significant implications in health contexts, where perceptions of control and agency are pivotal. Health threats are characterized by uncertainty and danger—conditions that intensify the drive to find explanations [11,34,35].

The literature suggests that individuals with an internal attributional style, or those who believe they can exert control over the causes of illness, are more likely to adopt health-promoting behaviors [36-38], including consistent adherence to treatment regimens [39-42]. Conversely, external or uncontrollable attributions (e.g., fate, genetics) are often associated with passivity or health-impairing behaviors [43-45].

These dynamics have been observed in response to large-scale public health threats as well. Internal attributions have been linked to increased likelihood of engaging in preventive measures such as mask-wearing, hand hygiene, and vaccination, particularly when fear of contagion is salient [46,47]. However, certain internal attributions—such as those involving anger or depressive moods—may reduce preventive behavior, as noted by Mo and Lau [42] in their study of the H1N1 pandemic. Similarly, high perceived controllability correlates with increased vaccine uptake, as demonstrated in research on invasive pneumococcal diseases [48], whereas noncontrol attributions hinder such behaviors [49].

Cultural factors also play a role in shaping attributional frameworks. Studies conducted in African contexts reveal that illness is often categorized as either a “normal” illness, treatable with biomedical medicine (or ‘white man’s medicine’), or an “unusual” illness, believed to be caused by supernatural forces and treated by traditional healers [50-52].

The present study

Given the established influence of causal attributions on health behaviors, this study investigates the explanatory models that individuals in Italy use to make sense of the exit from the COVID-19 crisis. Specifically, it examines which “exit strategies” people believe will lead to the end of the pandemic, how they evaluate these causes along the dimensions of locus, stability, and controllability, and whether these beliefs vary according to sociodemographic factors.

To do so, participants were asked to select one explanation from a predefined list of 14 possible causes, developed based on previous literature and pilot studies. They were then asked to evaluate the selected attribution using items adapted from the Causal Dimension Scale II [53]. This approach allowed for the analysis of both the content and structure of lay explanations.

By comparing participants’ responses to theoretical classifications found in the literature, we also sought to assess the accuracy and applicability of existing attributional models in real-world settings. In doing so, we address a challenge highlighted by Russell [ivi], known as the “fundamental attribution researcher error”: the tendency of researchers to misinterpret participants’ intentions or miscode the underlying attributional dimensions.

In summary, this theoretical framework integrates attribution theory, health psychology, and cultural considerations to contextualize the research questions. By examining how individuals cognitively and emotionally frame the pandemic’s resolution, the study aims to deepen our understanding of attributional processes in times of crisis, with potential implications for both theory and practice.

METHODS

Study design and population target

The study employed an analytical observational design aimed at exploring causal attributions related to exit strategies from the COVID-19 pandemic. The target population consisted of adults residing in Italy. Data collection was conducted online using a computer-assisted self-interviewing (CASI) approach via Google Forms. This method ensured anonymity and allowed participants to complete the questionnaire independently, requiring an average of 10 minutes to complete.

Sampling procedure and study instruments

The sampling procedure adopted a snowball technique, leveraging initial participants to recruit additional respondents through their networks. This method, suitable for exploratory research, enabled the recruitment of a diverse sample aligned with the study’s objectives. The final sample included 648 participants. A post hoc power analysis was conducted for the main chi-square tests reported in the study. Based on the observed effect sizes (w ranging from 0.199 to 0.228), the achieved statistical power was very high across all tests ($1 - \beta > 0.99$), assuming $\alpha = 0.05$ and sample size $N = 648$. These values indicate that the study was adequately powered to detect medium-sized effects in the relationships explored, particularly those involving causal dimensions and sociodemographic variables.

However, it is important to interpret these results with caution, given the use of a non-probabilistic sampling method. The sample consisted predominantly of women (68.9%), and the participants’ mean age was 34.9 years ($SD = 12.8$; range = 18–80). With regard to age, the only inclusion criterion was being 18 years or older. Educational backgrounds varied, with the most heavily represented groups of respondents were those with bachelor’s degrees (49.5%) and high school qualifications (33%). A total of 56% of the interviewees reported adhering to a religion. A total of 2.6% of the

respondents considered the strength of their religious faith and engagement to be poor (levels 1 and 2), whereas 39.7% rated religion as very important in their lives (levels 4 and 5).

An ad hoc semistructured questionnaire was developed by the authors for data collection. This questionnaire consisted of 41 questions that were grouped as follows.

After a brief description of the objectives of the study and a presentation of the informed consent form, sociodemographic information was collected. Respondents were asked to provide information about their age, gender, education level, and religion. The sociodemographic section included a total of nine questions.

Social representations of a pandemic and the vaccine: Following the concept of social representation proposed by Moscovici [54], respondents were asked to indicate the first three words that came to mind when thinking about the phrase “living in the period of the SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus pandemic” and the first three words related to the “SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus vaccine”. Participants were also asked to briefly explain the meaning they attributed to each of the six words provided. Overall, this section consisted of eight items, defined by the authors based on the technique developed by Pierre Vergès [96].

The area of causal attributions: The data presented in this study pertain to this area. Fourteen possible explanations for how the pandemic might come to an end were developed by the authors (based also on a previous similar study; see Norcia & Coli [55]) and were randomly presented to the participants, who were asked to choose the attribution that best fit their perception. The multiple-choice introductory question was as follows: “What do you rely on most to set your exit strategy from the threat of COVID? Please select one from the following list of alternatives”. The 14 possible alternatives were presented as follows:

1. *My status as a careful and thorough person will keep me safe.*
2. *My physique always resists diseases well.*
3. *Whether I feel able to cope with the threat of infection will depend a great deal on my mood.*
4. *I will be more careful in what I do (such as touching things).*
5. *It is a matter of fate.*
6. *I rely on God's love.*
7. *Vaccines and other medicines will protect me.*
8. *I am a good person; God will help me.*
9. *It is a matter of luck.*
10. *God has His plan; it will be what He wants.*
11. *The COVID-19 pandemic will end because the virus will gradually weaken until it becomes almost harmless.*
12. *I rely on what politicians say to do.*
13. *I rely on what doctors and experts say to do.*
14. *Others and their behaviors put me at risk; it is best to avoid contact with them as much as possible.*
15. *Other (open question).*

Subsequently, respondents were asked to rank the attribution they chose along a series of semantic differential scales representing the three causal dimensions. The items used were derived and adapted from the Revised Causal Dimension Scale - CDS II [56]. This scale can be considered an improvement over the original Causal Dimension Scale [53], according to its own authors, and its reliability and validity have been supported by numerous studies [56]. In the original study, Cronbach's alpha ranged from .67 to .82. Regarding construct validity, the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) yielded satisfactory fit indices. Even better fit values were reported in a recent study on the Italian translation

and validation of the CDSII (RMSEA = .06; CFI = .97; TLI = .96; $\chi^2/df = 2.68$) [97]. In the present study, Cronbach's alpha values for the scale used ranged from .69 to .99.

Table 1. Selected items from Causal Dimension Scale II.

<i>Instruction</i>	<i>If you were now to describe the alternative you selected in the previous question, what would you say?</i>						
Causal dimensions							
Controllability	I have power over it (that is, I can manage/influence it)	1	2	3	4	5	I have no power over it (that is, I can't manage/influence it)
	It is under the power of other people (that is, they can manage/influence it)	1	2	3	4	5	It is not under the power of other people (that is, they can't manage/influence it)
	Someone is actively responsible for it	1	2	3	4	5	Nobody is actively responsible for it
Stability	It is permanent	1	2	3	4	5	It is temporary
	It is stable over time	1	2	3	4	5	It is variable over time
Locus of causality	It reflects an aspect of myself	1	2	3	4	5	It reflects an aspect of the situation
	It is inside of me	1	2	3	4	5	It is outside of me
	It is about me	1	2	3	4	5	It is about others

Based on suggestions drawn from the literature (for a comprehensive taxonomy see, e.g., [21]; see also [20,53,57-60]) and the attributions made by participants in a previous study [55], the following clustering of different causal explanations into dimensional categories was adopted (Table 2).

Table 2. Clustering of causal explanations.

	Internal locus		External locus	
	Stable	Unstable	Stable	Unstable
Controllable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> My status as a careful and thorough person will keep me safe 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I will be more careful in what I do (such as touching things) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I rely on God's love. Vaccines and other medicines will protect me from the disease. I am a good person; God will help me. God has His plan; it will be what He wants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Others and their behaviors put me at risk; it is best to avoid contact with them as much as possible. I rely on what doctors and experts say to do I rely on what politicians say to do.
Uncontrollable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> My physique always resists disease well. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Whether I feel able to cope with the threat of infection will depend a great deal on my mood. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I will not be infected because the virus will gradually weaken until it becomes almost harmless. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is a matter of luck. It is a matter of fate.

The classification shown in the table above seems to be reasonably clear. For example, intentional behaviors, either one's own or those exhibited by other people, are always assessed as controllable; the former behaviors are internal and the latter are external. Hence, skills, unlike abilities (which are innate), are controllable and internal to the individual. Luck and fate are considered to be uncontrollable because they are not associated with volitional control but are rather unstable (unless we are discussing a lucky person, which refers to a stable trait) [57,59,60]. For transcendent attributions, previous studies have highlighted the fact that people most often refer to God [55]. Mallery et al. [61] observed that in the case of "pure" transcendent explanations (i.e., excluding mixed causes such as those perceived as controllable by a divine entity even if they are located in the environment), transcendent attributions can be viewed as external, controllable and stable; reasonably, a cause that is perceived as located in the divine entity is external (in most cases), and the entity in question is supposed to have control over it. Regarding stability, the scientific literature has highlighted the point that God's intervention is generally viewed as stable, mostly by individuals who are high in intrinsic religiousness [62]. In this circumstance, a perception of stability could originate from the perceived coherence of behavior displayed by God across time and situations, even when it is considered to be elicited by an individual's acts (such as his prayers or sins).

Preliminarily, data were preprocessed by grouping respondents based on their age and level of education. In terms of age, respondents were classified into 5 groups: up to 29 years, 30-39 years, 40-49 years, 50-59 years, and 60+ years. Age groups were defined post hoc to maximize significance for between-group comparisons while also maintaining a reasonable degree of separation between groups. On the other hand, with regard to the level of education, the following groups were defined: junior high school graduation (11-14 y.o.), high school graduation (15-19 y.o.), bachelor's degree, postgraduate degree.

Once the data were prepared, descriptive statistics were computed, including the mean and standard deviation, to provide a comprehensive description of the sample.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics® version 23 software [65], including descriptive statistics, chi-square tests for group comparisons. An alpha level of 0.05 was set for each series of chi-square analyses. The agreement rate between causal dimensionality as defined in the scientific literature and as indicated by respondents was measured using Cohen's kappa coefficient [63]. The authors referred to Cohen [64] for the range and recommended interpretation of effect sizes: small = 0.10–0.34; medium = 0.35–0.6; large => 0.60. Preliminary results were clustered based on sociodemographic characteristics such as age and educational level to identify significant differences in causal attributions and causal dimensions.

RESULTS

Results regarding causal attributions

As shown in Table 3, most respondents identified following the advice of doctors and experts as the most effective way out of the pandemic. This alternative was chosen by more than 1 in 3 respondents (35%). A close second to this choice (33.8%) was represented by those who, on the other hand, chose to rely on their own preventive behaviors, such as being careful about touching objects or interacting with specific people or places. Finally, a noteworthy share of respondents highlighted vaccines and other medicines as their solution. This alternative was chosen by nearly 1 in 5 respondents (19.2%). The alternatives examined thus far, taken together, cover nearly 90% of the responses, thus making the remaining alternatives residual. It is interesting to note that fewer than 5% of respondents claimed that they would resign themselves to the "will" of fortune or fate, while just over 1.5% chose religious attributions (God's plan or God's love). Notably, none of the respondents claimed to rely on what politicians indicated.

Table 3. Most frequently chosen attributions.

Item	Frequency	Valid percentage
I rely on what doctors and experts say to do.	215	35.0
I will be more careful in what I do (such as touching things)	208	33.8
Vaccines and other medicines will protect me from the disease.	118	19.2
It is a matter of luck.	15	2.4
My status as a careful and thorough person will keep me safe	15	2.4
It is a matter of fate.	13	2.1
God has His plan; it will be what He wants.	7	1.1
My physique always resists disease well.	7	1.1
I will not be infected because the virus will gradually weaken until it becomes almost harmless.	7	1.1
It will depend a great deal on my mood.	4	0.7
I rely on God's love.	3	0.5
Others and their behaviors put me at risk; it is best to avoid contact with them as much as possible.	3	0.5
I rely on what politicians say to do.	0	0
I am a good person; God will not punish me	0	0
Total	615	100.0
<i>Missing</i>	33	
Total	648	

Results regarding causal dimensions

With regard to the description of exit strategies from the pandemic phase in terms of causal dimensions, Table 4 shows which sides of the dimensions were chosen most frequently by respondents. This step, in the authors' opinion, helped ensure better coherence between the collected information and people's real perceptions. As shown in Table 4, the respondents included in this specific sample, when considering the path out of this pandemic phase, had in mind events/behaviors that mainly affected themselves (74.7%) rather than others (25.3%). Respondents claimed that these events/behaviors were something for which someone is actively responsible (72.9%), which is not stable over time but can instead vary (66.3%), and over which, in nearly 60% of cases, the individual believes that he or she is able to intervene. These characteristics are the aspects that, according to respondents, best characterize the exit strategies they chose. With respect to the remaining aspects, respondents expressed less clear-cut opinions, and preferences were distributed in a substantially equal manner between the poles of the semantic differential. The findings show that when asked to describe their chosen alternatives in terms of their causal dimensions, respondents provided descriptions that exhibited a degree of coherence with the taxonomy found in the scientific literature ranging from medium to large (Cohen's kappa = 0.53 < k < 0.64).

Table 4. Most frequently chosen causal dimensions.

More frequently chosen alternatives	%	Less frequently chosen alternatives	%
It is about me	74.7	It is about others	25.3
Someone is actively responsible for it	72.9	Nobody is actively responsible for it	27.1
It is variable over time	66.3	It is stable over time	33.7
I have power over it (that is, I can manage/influence it)	57.9	I have no power over it (that is, I can't manage/influence it)	42.1
It reflects an aspect of the situation	53.9	It reflects an aspect of myself	46.1
It is outside of me	53.6	It is inside of me	46.4
It is not under the power of other people (that is, they can't manage/influence it)	52.4	It is under the power of other people (that is, they can't manage/influence it)	47.6
It is temporary	52.2	It is permanent	47.8

Causal dimensions and sociodemographic information

Regarding the observable relationships between respondents' sociodemographic characteristics and the causal dimensions related to the chosen attribution, few significant findings emerged, and those findings that did emerge pertained only to age and level of education. Stability and control were the causal dimensions in which the greatest differences were evident. With regard to the former, younger age groups, especially the 18-29 y.o. range, seemed to most frequently describe the chosen attribution as permanent and stable. As age increased, however, choices leaned more toward temporality ($\chi^2 = 33,689$, $p = 0.006$) and variability ($\chi^2 = 30,749$, $p = 0.014$). A significant, albeit weak, relationship also emerged in the case of the causal dimension control. In this case, both younger (18-29 y.o.) and older (60-99 y.o.) respondents chose the extreme poles more frequently, in contrast to the other age groups, who chose equidistance most frequently ($\chi^2 = 25,786$, $p = 0.057$). The significance of the relationship increases after taking level of education into consideration. In fact, as level of education increased, the idea that a responsible individual can be identified in the event/behavior related to the pathway out of the pandemic phase increased while (and it seems automatic but is not) the idea that no such responsible individual can be identified decreased ($\chi^2 = 29$, $p = 0.004$).

DISCUSSION

Since this research is an exploratory study based on a nonrepresentative sample, the conclusions are closer to insights than to an actual verification of relationships and trends. The proposed insights, however, can facilitate the formulation of interpretative hypotheses.

The general impression that emerges from reading respondents' most frequently chosen answers (which, taken together, account for nearly 90 % of preferences) indicates an active overall attitude toward the "path out" from this dramatically peculiar period: Respondents chose behavior in which they felt themselves to be intensely involved and over which they perceived they could exercise power despite the fact that the behavior in question was perceived as external to them in some cases.

Examining what respondents chose among the proposed causal attributions in further detail, the most preferred alternative ("I rely on what doctors and experts say to do") seems to consist of going to the source of information based on a kind of conscious reliance and without any intermediaries whatsoever: any filter between experts and the population, i.e., politicians, was definitely excluded by respondents.

The will and need to access the source of information directly, bypassing filters or intermediaries, may have been favored basically for two reasons. First, the massive presence of doctors and experts in the mass media has given

people a way to remain informed (perhaps not always in a linear and coherent way) and to develop some expertise about the virus, its dynamics and ways to protect themselves from it. Accordingly, when people are asked to indicate a path out of this dramatic phase, it is intuitive for them to include seeking the advice of doctors and experts. The second aspect concerns people's general distrust of politics. Politicians, in fact, repeatedly conveyed mixed messages—especially at the beginning of the pandemic—and in many cases gave the impression that they were using the emergency as a ground for the usual loop of mutual accusations.

Now, consider the second and the third alternatives in order of the number of preferences. These alternatives refer to being careful about the objects one touches/places one frequents and the use of vaccines and other medicines, respectively. Additionally, both of these behaviors exhibit the characteristics of intentionality, controllability and autonomy (i.e., people perceive that they can enact them on their own; [66], thus confirming the active attitude previously detected in respondents' choices. An additional factor that could be worth considering is that these alternatives refer to preventive or precautionary behaviors, that is, measures aimed at reducing disease transmission through social distancing, face mask wearing or similar behaviors. Even the vaccine, a medicine that has almost totally polarized communication in this area, can be considered “preventive” since its fundamental characteristic is to prevent the occurrence of the disease.

Uncertainty and its influence on the ways in which people remain informed, could be the most relevant *trait d'union* among the first three alternatives chosen by respondents: As the quantity of information and information sources increase, people often struggle to manage a tremendous amount of new information [67] and thereby experience uncertainty. Furthermore, Chowdhury et al. [68] noted that the proliferation of information sources may produce an even stronger feeling of uncertainty that may persist after the process of information seeking and retrieval has been completed (“persistent uncertainty”) instead of decreasing. In addition, it is interesting to note that an affective response to a risk (e.g., worry) may increase uncertainty because it raises the information sufficiency threshold, thus widening the gap between what one knows and what one needs to know [69].

In general, recent scientific literature has noted a general increase in the number of people who choose to play an active role in their health management [70]. Uncertainty may also have increased a trend previously highlighted in the literature, namely, the tendency for people to turn more frequently to their doctors for health information, mostly in cases of perceived serious health threats and direct experience [71]. Given the strong presence of the topic of “COVID-19” in our daily lives over the past 2 years, we may claim that we have all had direct experience of the pandemic.

Accordingly, the scientific literature has highlighted a close relation between high uncertainty, mostly in the presence of health threats, and the ways in which people handle the search for information. The uncertainty originating from the perception that people have an insufficient amount of information - driven, in our case, by conflicting indications from the world of politics and medicine itself [72] - may have motivated people to engage in a more active, more systematic and less routine search for information (i.e., bypassing the usual information channels). An overview of the scientific literature also reveals a relation between uncertainty and engagement in preventive behaviors, which is mediated by the intervention of some variables such as fear (related to uncertainty. [73] and risk perception [74-76]: With regard to infectious diseases, people are more likely to engage in preventive behaviors if they perceive that there is a tangible risk of contagion and that the disease might have severe consequences.

The hypotheses proposed above to account for people's observed information-seeking styles and adoption/maintenance of preventive behaviors can also be explained by reference to several prominent scientific models. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB; [77,78]; and Heuristic-Systematic Model (HSM; see [79], for example, shed light on how uncertainty and the characteristics of a perceived hazard (e.g., personal risk or trust in scientific institutions) may motivate people to more actively seek information. In addition, the Risk Information Seeking and

Processing model (RISP; see [69], one of the most widely used models in explorations of information seeking and processing, which is somehow related to the two models cited above, could also help clarify the relationship between the perceived insufficient or unsatisfactory amount of information – which could originate from an excessive number of opinions, which may occasionally conflict with one another – and the motivation to invest in information seeking and behavioral change, often in a preventive direction (ivi).

To recapitulate, a number of factors, such as the excessive amount of (sometimes conflicting) sources of information, the perceived insufficient amount of information and the struggle to reach subjectively satisfactory levels of confidence in one's information regarding the health threat, a pervasive feeling of uncertainty, and the strong perception of a risk, recursively influence each other and often promote more active and systematic information seeking and behavioral change/adoption of preventive behaviors in people.

When examining what actually occurred worldwide since the onset of the pandemic, it is easy to notice the stressful situation, strong uncertainty and perceived uncontrollability that have arisen [2,48,80]. These characteristics resulted from the set of factors mentioned above but also, for example, from the lack of clear knowledge pertaining to critical information such as the factors of contagion [81], the efficacy of existing treatments and the availability of beds equipped with oxygen therapy and ventilators for intensive care. This picture of what happened and the challenges that people have faced could include, in the authors' opinion, the factors that, according to the scientific literature, may have motivated people to adopt the active attitudes toward information seeking and the stronger disposition toward preventive/precautionary behaviors that emerged from the answers given by the respondents.

Study limitations

Despite the relevance of the findings, this study presents several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the sampling procedure relied on a non-probabilistic snowball approach and this inevitably limits the generalizability of the results. Given that participants were self-selected, the sample may not be representative of the Italian population, thus potentially introducing selection bias. The overrepresentation of women (68.9%) and younger adults (mean age = 34.9 years) in the sample may have also influenced the attributional patterns observed, particularly in relation to the dimensions of controllability and stability.

Second, while the questionnaire was constructed with reference to validated instruments (i.e., the Revised Causal Dimension Scale II), the adaptations may have affected the psychometric properties of the items.

Finally, the forced-choice structure of the attributional question may have constrained the richness and complexity of respondents' views. Although an open-ended "other" option was available, the reliance on predefined alternatives may have overlooked nuanced or mixed attributions, such as those that integrate both personal agency and structural or transcendent explanations. This constraint may have contributed to the predominance of a few alternatives and underestimated the diversity of interpretative frames adopted by participants.

Future research and implications

Future research should aim to address these limitations by employing more representative sampling methods, longitudinal designs, and mixed-method approaches capable of capturing the multidimensional nature of causal attribution in health crises. Although this study is solely exploratory in nature, some of its findings may have useful implications both in terms of theoretical advancement and practical suggestions.

The most critical aspects certainly pertain to the pervasive sense of uncertainty and the corresponding perception of risk that people experienced during the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic. After discussing the potential causes underlying these unpleasant feelings, we can speculate on some practical suggestions that might be helpful.

Certainly, one plan that it would be useful to implement concerns the quality and quantity of information made available to people, from both a content and a process perspective. The *tsunami of information* mentioned by Zarocostas

[82], which was amplified exponentially by social media, has repeatedly and in multiple ways functioned as a detrimental factor in the management and containment of infection. This point applies to politicians and experts who have highlighted ineffective treatments [83], made unmotivated and upsetting about-faces, or downplayed the risk by describing COVID-19 as a normal flu [8,9,84]; as well as by word of mouth that has encouraged the spread of incorrect and potentially dangerous information. With regard to *quantity*, the massive amount of information—in many cases discordant—originating from an excessive plurality of voices that have been given space made it difficult for people to properly understand, classify, and therefore master the available information, which could have decreased their fear and anxiety.

In this regard, some suggestions can be made. In this context, a comprehensive framework strategy is needed, in which trusted community agents such as politicians, technicians, and health workers on the one hand and social media managers and media technicians on the other are involved. This strategy should focus on the sharing of advice, guidelines and information, the rapid transmission of urgent information, and the careful selection of essential information, tempering unwanted media overexposure. As has been seen in other health emergencies, social media expand people's access to information about a wide range of health issues, regardless of education, age, race, or ethnicity [85-87], and it has been seen to often outperform official channels in the dissemination of information, especially in terms of timeliness [88,89]. It is therefore worth stressing the importance of not considering social media as a marginal and complementary channel [90], but rather of harnessing their enormous potential for knowledge dissemination as a key point in this strategy. The first suggestion that should be made, in the authors' opinion, is to act on misinformation [91]. In addition, implementing interventions aimed at stemming the tide of poor-quality information by impeding the dissemination of incorrect, contradictory, or overabundant information, which spread widely through the media in the case of COVID-19, could help reduce the sense of uncertainty that has, as previously seen, a major impact on people both on an emotional and a behavioral level. Information regarding public health should be examined prior to its dissemination, for example, to eliminate ambiguities - which can produce dangerous misunderstandings - and ensure understanding by subjects who exhibit different characteristics. In this regard, it might be useful for information to be prescreened by groups of subjects that exhibit variety in terms of, for example, age, level of education or digital literacy [92].

As a second key point, if, on the one hand, it is important that information is usable by people who exhibit different characteristics, on the other hand, being able to properly intercept the changing information needs expressed by people – possibly using AI or big data [92] – also seems to be crucial to improve the quality of information. In this case, the utility of this approach could be twofold since it not only offers greater assurance of providing information that is more useful but can also foster the reinforcement of positive attitudes on the part of people, such as trust in community agencies as reliable sources of crisis information. The principle just described, i.e., *Providing useful information to a variety of publics* is a primary norm of *dialogic communication* [93], that is, a form of communication management that public relation practitioners use to successfully relate to their publics, which encourages the exchange of ideas and opinions. *Ease of use* and *dialogic loops* are other key principles of dialogic communication that may also benefit the quality of information. These principles refer, respectively, to making it feasible for people to understand the provided content and handle it easily and to allowing people to ask questions and provide feedback [94]. The dialogic communication model could definitely inspire institutional communication, thus increasing people's perception that proper attention is being given to mutual understanding and shared decision-making as well as that information is specifically tailored to their own characteristics and needs. This approach may increase people's empowerment and engagement, that is, their willingness to actively share and respond, thus making them more receptive to the information provided by community agencies.

Finally, sharing success stories may help reduce uncertainty. On the one hand, success stories can help policy-makers better understand what is happening in some specific situations and can help people learn from each other's experiences. On the other hand, these stories can refine people's perceptions of the actual situation by providing them with more elements and references [95], thus decreasing their uncertainty by ensuring a better balance between perceived reality and expectations. Additionally, in this case, social media may play a pivotal role since they have the potential to allow people to easily share their experiences and discuss matters with their peers in a way that traditional websites do not.

In summary, when participants in our study were asked to consider the paths that they could take to exit the COVID-19 pandemic emergency period most effectively, they almost exclusively referred to 3 causes. These causes seem to primarily invoke a strong motivation to inform themselves by going directly to the source and engaging in preventive behaviors. According to a review of the scientific literature that also referred to specific models [98-100], it seems that the recurring theme underlying what emerged was uncertainty, which was exacerbated by the presence of a serious health hazard. Looking back at what has happened in Italy since the beginning of the pandemic, it is easy to see how uncertainty, which was exacerbated by overabundant and often contradictory communication and fear, was a strongly prevalent theme in people's experience. Interventions that could help in this situation, according to the authors, should involve close collaboration between decision-makers and technicians in institutions and communication channels—primarily social media—and should primarily aim to improve the quality of information. This challenge is therefore a matter of increasing the upstream focus on both the selection of the disseminated content and its disseminators. Provision should also be made to ensure that the corresponding content meets the different information needs expressed by people and is understandable by all, taking into account, for example, people's different ages or levels of education. Furthermore, regarding content, the dissemination of success stories through the sharing of experiences and lived experiences could help give more substance to people's perceptions. Finally, moving beyond the “content” to focus on the “container”, it might be useful to refer to dialogic communication management models, which, by promoting dialog and the ease of information retrieval, help decrease people's sense of uncertainty.

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